

UNITED4Surveillance pilot report (Poland)

1. Describe the aim and objectives of your pilot study

In Poland, we focused on rotavirus infections (annually, between 20,000 and 35,000 cases are reported — incidence rate: 60–89 per 100,000), with approximately 90% of reported cases requiring hospitalization. The aim of the pilot was to explore the potential for strengthening surveillance based on rotavirus infections by analyzing the structure and availability of existing data collected across different components of the healthcare system, as well as the types of variables recorded, and by identifying opportunities to improve data completeness and interoperability, while also aiming to reduce workload and avoid duplication in data gathering.

2. Describe the expected output prior to start of the pilot

The primary aim of the pilot was to explore the feasibility of improving data integration for rotavirus surveillance in Poland by identifying available data sources, assessing their compatibility, and uncovering potential legal and organizational barriers. Expected outputs included: 1) gathering knowledge about variables and their format collected by other systems, 2) identification of potential linkage points to understand where integration might be legally possible.

3. Briefly describe the method(s) used

The methodological approach was primarily qualitative and descriptive, based on case-based system analysis. Key steps included: 1) identification of major data sources across public (epidemiological surveillance, data collected by the public insurance institution and hospital morbidity studies) and private (laboratory data) sectors, followed by an assessment of their availability, completeness, and interoperability; 2) evaluation of real-life integration challenges through a practical review of existing systems. Drawing on our experience from the pilot, we present an exploratory mapping of the legal, technical, and organizational barriers hindering the integration of routinely collected data relevant for public health surveillance in Poland. We used the Ishikawa (Fishbone) diagram to systematically categorize findings: A) We began by defining the central problem: barriers to integration of data; B) Next we identified and classified primary causes into six categories: 1) environment – related to the overall protection of data and the legal framework; 2) management – referred to the data policy; 3) processes – addressing the procedures designed for data collection in systems; 4) technology – including tools, infrastructure, data formats, and system interoperability; 5) manpower - concerned the personnel, burden of work, knowledge and awareness of the importance of data for public health; 6) data – addressed the data quality, completeness, and standardization across systems; C) Within each category, sub-causes were added.

4. Report the principal finding(s) of your pilot study

We identified a range of systemic, legal, technical, and organizational barriers that limit the integration of routinely collected data for public health surveillance. These findings were synthesized and categorized into six thematic areas: environment, management, processes, technology, manpower and data.

1. Environment

The legal environment proved to be one of the most significant barriers to data integration. Due to the unclear legal provisions for integrating data for public health surveillance, institutions maintain strict protection of health data collected in their systems.

2. Management

One important gap identified is the absence of a national policy guiding data sharing and integration across institutions.

We observed challenges related to lack of obligatory reporting mechanisms. When reporting was not mandatory (such as in the case of the e-vaccination card), or when a disease was not included in European-level surveillance systems (such as rotavirus, which is mandatory under national-level surveillance), it was often deprioritized in practice.

We identified legal and ethical concerns regarding the potential de-anonymization of previously anonymous data when linked with identifiable sources.

3. Processes

Each system tends to operate independently, often without a clear approach to data integration. Systems are generally designed to function autonomously and to gather the necessary data individually, rather than through coordinated input from other sources.

Transparency in system descriptions is available in a clear form for those datasets collected as part of official public statistics.

Surveillance processes are designed with limited data collected at the notification stage from physicians and laboratory (e.g. via the universal disease form). This necessitates additional supplementary actions, such as contacting hospitals to complete information, which increases workload. In many cases, paper-based notification must be manually enter into electronic systems by staff at local public health authority.

Anonymized data collected in specific contexts (e.g. hospital morbidity study) cannot be linked or used in broader surveillance due to legal and ethical concerns about potential de-anonymization.

4. Technology

The technological landscape of systems is heterogeneous, as different systems were developed at various times and for different purposes. Institutions may adopt different models for maintaining their systems (e.g., in-house IT staff vs. outsourcing to external service providers). These differences can influence the extra cost, or ability to integrate with other systems.

5. Manpower

Physicians and laboratory personnel, who are reporting suspected or diagnosed cases of infectious diseases, are often overburdened, limiting their capacity. They frequently perceive this task as an administrative obligation rather than a meaningful contribution to public health. There is often a lack of understanding about the value of surveillance data for supporting public health measures, informing health policymakers, and guiding the development of prevention strategies. At this stage, data protection regulations such as GDPR are interpreted in various ways across organizations, which contributes to uncertainty. This often results in a more cautious approach when reporting involves sharing patient health data with local public health authorities, due to concerns about potential legal violations. At this stage as well, in cases where part of surveillance process is not mandatory, it is often omitted, for example, even if electronic forms are available, they are often underused because their use is not required. As a result, paper-based notification forms are still used, requiring local health authority staff to manually enter this information into electronic systems, which increases their workload.

The availability of programmers and IT support may vary depending on the model adopted for system maintenance.

6. Data

Data-related issues can be among the most relevant limitations. In different systems, data quality may vary and missing or incomplete variables can be relatively common. Indicators may also be defined differently, which can pose challenges for data integration and analysis. There may also be a general lack of metadata - such as information on structure, meaning, and coding of data - which can make it more difficult to interpret and combine information across systems. The use of different formats and definitions by various systems often requires additional mapping.

The risk of de-anonymization may persist.

5. Formulate your main take-away(s) and recommendations of your pilot study and provide rationale(s)

The pilot shows that one of the most significant barriers to achieving effective data integration is the lack of clear legal mechanisms regarding the secure exchange of sensitive data among existing systems. Establishing a more clearly defined legal and governance framework could be an important step toward facilitating the safe sharing and integration of data for public health surveillance purposes.

6. Reflect on most relevant limitations and/or challenges (including potential solutions) and the degree of achieving expected output of your pilot study

The main limitation observed during the pilot appeared to be the presence of significant legal barriers to accessing and integrating data from different systems. Despite these challenges, the pilot enabled the mapping of available data sources, the identification of barriers and the prioritization of areas for further consideration. Developing a legal framework that could support data exchange may represent an important step toward building a more integrated surveillance system.

7. Did your pilot study contribute to strengthened (inter)national infectious disease surveillance? Why or why not?

Yes. The pilot provided a valuable opportunity to focus on data that are often overlooked due to high workload and the absence of mandatory reporting at the European level. By focusing on rotavirus and identifying key structural barriers using the fishbone (Ishikawa) method, the findings offer a transferable framework that can support improvements in data integration and surveillance for all infectious diseases under mandatory surveillance.

UNITED4Surveillance legal/privacy barriers (template)

1. To what degree did you experience legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study?

No	Little	Some	Large	Very large
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Legal barriers were identified as the most significant challenge encountered during the pilot study, strongly influencing the feasibility of data integration.

2. If so, please provide a detailed example(s) on the experienced legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study.

In Poland, data are strictly protected. A key challenge encountered was the lack of specific legal regulations that would directly allow the sharing or linking of individual-level, non-anonymized data across different systems. We also identified a potential issue concerning the risk of de-anonymization of data that were originally collected in an anonymous form. When integrating such data with other sources, there is a possibility that individuals could be re-identified, raising important legal and ethical concerns.

3. How did you cope with and/or solve the experienced legal and/or privacy barrier within your pilot study? If not, what is your suggestion to solve this legal/privacy barrier(s) in the future?

Due to the structural nature of the legal barriers, no direct solution could be implemented during the pilot. To address this challenge in the future, it may be necessary to develop a national legal framework for integrating data for public health surveillance purposes.